

The Main Causes of the Development of Diseases of the Biliary System in Children, Their Importance and Relevance in Medicine

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ABSTRACT: The presented analysis presents the results of a brief review of the literature devoted to the analysis of the occurrence, development and diagnosis of diseases of the hepatobiliary system in children, as well as achievements and shortcomings in treatment. The conducted analyses have shown that today the prevalence and development of obesity worldwide, especially in young children, is increasing every day, and the development of obesity in these children and adolescents is the main modifiable risk factors in the pathogenesis of pathologies of the liver and biliary tract. Based on the above information, the implementation of successful measures for the prevention and treatment of obesity can make a huge contribution to reducing the incidence of the hepatobiliary system by a certain amount.

KEY WORDS: Hepatobiliary system, gastrointestinal tract, metabolic syndrome; gallstones, obesity, hepatobiliary arteria

RELEVANCE

It is known that the hepatobiliary system (GBS) is a complex, multilevel system consisting of such parts as the parenchymal part - hepatocytes and the cavity - bile ducts, as well as the sphincter. This system, thanks to the harmonious distribution of all departments, provides one of its important functions for the body – the functions of digestion and excretion. Functional disorders of the gastrointestinal system are most often observed in childhood, and in pediatric practice, the diagnosis of "functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract" as a nosological unit is made with certain difficulties to this day. The importance of recognized functional disorders is determined not only by their prevalence, but also by the fact that violations of the motor activity of the gastrointestinal tract in childhood are the cause of subsequent serious disorders of the digestive system. More than 80% of children with digestive diseases have various disorders of the hepatobiliary system (GBS), and liver and biliary tract diseases in this regard occupy a leading position among all pathologies of the gastrointestinal system. The presence of a percentage of unfavorable environmental factors in the etiology of hepatobiliary pathologies from 14 to 36% indicates that children in unfavorable sanitary and hygienic conditions are 3-4 times more common than those who are conditionally "clean" [1-6]. This, in turn, not only worsens the quality of life and health of patients, but also negatively affects social and professional adaptation. The diagnosis of FDBS is made with fatty, excluding organic diseases, in a regular clinic. Considering that anomalies or structural features of the biliary tract and gallbladder (GI) in children are increasingly being investigated, it is recommended to distinguish dyskinesia in accordance with the functional state of the biliary apparatus: hypomotor (hypokinetic) and hypermotor (hyperkinetic) dyskinesia. According to many authors, the most common form in children is hypermotor (hyperkinetic) dyskinesia. A violation of synchronicity in the work of the LC and the sphincter apparatus underlies the FDBS and causes the formation of clinical symptoms [7-12]. Currently, the number of patients with hepatobiliary pathology exceeds 2 billion people. According to the World Health Organization, there is currently a clear trend towards an increase in the number of patients with hepatobiliary pathology. In this regard, in recent years, the problem of diseases of the hepatobiliary system of various etiologies has become extremely relevant [13].

THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Conducting a brief analysis of the literature on the origin, development, significance and relevance of diseases of the hepatobiliary system in modern medicine.

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THE REASONS THAT ARE IN THE MAIN PLACE IN THE OCCURRENCE OF DISEASES OF THE HEPATOBILIARY SYSTEM

Medicine, including in the practice of hepatology, has for many years received a clinic for the study of diseases of the hepatobiliary system, which are common in children and are considered a problem, and scientific and practical work is carried out within the clinic. With pathologies of the liver and biliary tract, a large number of children's appeals mainly attract attention, thanks to which a number of biochemical analyses were carried out in registered patients and healthy children, determination of serum carbohydrates and lipids, analysis of ultrasound examinations of the hepatobiliary system, which is carried out regularly. Studies have shown that the majority of overweight children have non-alcoholic fatty liver disease and an increase in the level of liver enzymes by a third, as well as changes in the colloidal composition of bile [14-16]. According to the Jackson World Health Organization, the prevalence of metabolic disorders, overweight and obesity among children and adolescents is high, and this pathology worldwide over the past 10 years has amounted to more than 40 million among 5-year-olds, out of millions among children aged 5-19 years, more than registered. In the conducted studies, there is a high incidence of complications among obese children, mainly in adolescence, and especially among the adult population complications: arterial hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus, non-alcoholic fatty hepatitis, cholelithiasis. In recent years, many studies have assessed the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among various ethnic groups and groups of people of different ages, and as a result of surveys, the relationship between obesity and vitamin D deficiency has been revealed [17,18]. Many variants of anomalies in the development of the biliary tract usually do not show clinical signs and, although they have no clinical significance, there are anomalies that can significantly contribute to the pathogenesis of diseases of the biliary system itself and other organs (liver, pancreas, esophagus, stomach and intestines) that aggravate their course contributes to the cessation of diseases, while viral infections are also the leading causes of liver and biliary tract pathologies in children. Below, the causes of diseases of the hepatobiliary system are fixed in tabular form based on the analyses performed [19,20].

Table 1. Causes leading to hepatobiliary pathology.

<i>N</i>	Diseases	Frequency of occurrence in %
1.	Viral liver diseases	45-50
2.	Metabolic disorders, obesity	30-35
3.	Disorders of the liver and biliary tract	5-10
4.	Other diseases	2-3

As shown in the table, although viral diseases are at the forefront in the development of hepatobiliary disorders in children, the importance of metabolic disorders or overweight is no less important

Epidemiology of the causes of diseases of the hepatobiliary system.

Based on the conducted scientific studies, the authors believe that liver damage is an important factor in the development of metabolic syndrome, and also that with the development of non-alcoholic fatty liver hepatitis, there is a violation of bile formation and bile secretory function. Among children, there are data on the occurrence of non-alcoholic fatty liver hepatitis in 70% of obese children, with metabolic syndrome - in 85% of children [21]. In elderly patients with disorders of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, pathology of the biliary tract is more common [22, 23]. About 67% of obese children show symptoms of non-alcoholic hepatitis of the liver, and one in three (about 34%) had an increase in ALT levels, indicating that they developed non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. In children with metabolic syndrome, acute disorders of the functional state of the associated bile tract are formed, in which, along with the physico-chemical composition of the grass, its motor-evacuation activity is also disrupted. As a result, every third child (35-37%) has violations of the colloidal composition of bile, which manifest themselves in the form of gallstone disease, occurring with a predominance of the stage of stone formation in the gallbladder. At the same time, every third (33-34%) child from overweight children shows signs of diffuse cholestasis of the gallbladder, which is accompanied by gallstone disease of various stages [24, 25,26]. Also, 1 out of 5-25 thousand newborns have hepatobiliary arteria, which accounts for more than 45% of hepatobiliary pathologies [27].

Problems in the diagnosis of diseases of the hepatobiliary system and their discussion. Despite the progress made in the diagnosis and treatment of diseases of the hepatobiliary system, these pathologies have not lost their importance and relevance even today [28-34]. Because with each diagnostic method, along with high accuracy, there will also be a risk of serious complications [35-40]. In this regard, the implementation of measures for the timely perfect diagnosis and treatment of liver diseases is an important, extremely urgent problem faced by modern medicine, and which cannot be postponed [41-44].

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CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the prevalence and development of obesity in young children, in particular, worldwide, is increasing every day, and the development of obesity in these children and adolescents is the main modifiable risk factors in the pathogenesis of pathologies of the liver and biliary tract. Based on the above information, the implementation of successful measures for the prevention and treatment of obesity can make a huge contribution to reducing the incidence of the hepatobiliary system by a certain amount. Also among them is the timely detection of pathologies of the liver and biliary tract in newborns.

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